

Utilization Of Item Difficulty, Discrimination, And Distracter Analysis With Kuder-Richardson 20 And Rasch Model (3D-KRM) To Examine Psychometric Properties Of Term Examination In Calculus

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Test construction has a step-by-step procedure to be done before an examination is given to the intended students. Starting from the test of objectives, type of test, table of specifications, drafting, up to try-out, and validation, each step has its own process to ensure the constructed test is valid, reliable, and usable. The teachers in higher education seemed to follow the first four steps, but the last step was often neglected due to its rigorous process, which makes it complex. For this reason, the validity and reliability of term examinations distributed to students are compromised. With this, a psychometric guide is needed to address the presented issue. In this study, the item difficulty index, discrimination, distractors' efficiency, Kuder-Richardson 20, and Rasch model (3D-KRM) were used to analyze psychometric properties of an examination given to 19 purposively selected students in the Calculus subject. A 50-item test was given to the respondents. Out of 50 items, only 31 items were considered reliable after passing the 3D-KRM analysis. These items are recommended for the finalization of the test for future use.

Key words: *Item Difficulty, Discrimination, Distracter Analysis, Kuder-Richardson 20, Rasch Model*

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INTRODUCTION

Examination is a crucial part of any academic undertaking [1]. It is the moment where students' need to provide their own learnings for evaluation purposes. As part of the educational process, examination is the eventual or last step. After the examination, students are evaluated based on the marks they obtained, whether passed or failed. For this reason, term examination should be given attention specifically in the preparation to serve its objective purpose of measuring what students learned from the semestral lectures and activities. However, not all education practitioners pay close attention to the difficulty and reliability of term examinations given to students due to its requirement of expertise and time time-consuming sequential process [2] and lack of requisite skills in test construction procedures[3]. Hence, a test given to the students seems questionable. As a result, the pureness of the examination's objectivity is compromised. With this, strong action is needed to ensure that the term examination is well-prepared before it is given to the intended test takers (students). Thus, this study is conceptualized to strengthen the term examination given to the students using different psychometric measurements, such as the item difficulty index, index of discrimination as two parameters of dichotomous data [4], distracter analysis [5], Kuder-Richardson 20 [6], [7], and Rasch model estimation [8], [9], [10]. In addition, this study may open an opportunity to teachers to be equipped with test construction procedures. Likewise, this study aims to propose a college policy about validity, difficulty, and reliability checking of examinations before administering to students.

The test construction is a crucial part of educational assessment. In this part, the teacher needs to prepare a test that is valid and reliable. In addition, each item in the examination should be carefully analyzed depending on its complexity through item analysis. In item analysis, teachers need to check the item difficulty index, index of discrimination, and status of distracters. After this, the teacher needs to check the reliability of the test. In this study, the researchers will use the Kuder-Richardson 20 and Rasch model to estimate the reliability of the term examination given to the students of College of Teacher Education.

OBJECTIVES

This study aims to strengthen the reliability of major examinations given to the College of Teacher Education using psychometric reliability measures such as KR-20 and Rasch model. In particular, it aims to:

1. determine the item difficulty index of each item presented in each major examination;
2. determine the index of discrimination of each item presented in each major examination;
3. examine the distracters presented in each item for each major examination;
4. determine the reliability of the major examination using KR-20;
5. determine the reliability of the major examination using Rasch model;
6. propose a policy focusing on strengthening the reliability of term exams in the College of Teacher Education.

METHODOLOGY

The university where the study is conducted, in its learning continuity plan, allocates 40% for term examinations. This percent allocation is for both the midterm and final examinations. Apart from this, the remaining 60% is intended for class engagement (20%), learning outputs (20%), and quizzes (20%). Considering this university's grading policy, examination plays a major role in students' success or failure in a particular semester for each course/subject they take. Given the situation, there is a need to pay attention to the validity and reliability of each term examination given to students.

This program adopts a multi-method approach of research, specifically exploratory-developmental. This approach combines both quantitative design, such as descriptive (on exploratory part), and developmental research. Respondents of the study will include 19 purposively chosen education students enrolled in Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics. To achieve the research objectives, descriptive exploratory statistical methods will be employed, including frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation. Likewise, the study uses the index of difficulty, index of discrimination, Distractor efficiency, Kuder-Richardson 20, and Rasch model to analyze each test item in the examination given to the students.

The researcher adopted the 6-stage test construction process proposed by [11] starting from (1) planning and defining the test objectivity, (2) choosing an appropriate scaling method, (3) constructing the items, (4) assessing and testifying the items, (5) reinventing and revising the test, (6) and finalizing and executing or publishing the test.

For the first stage, the learning outcomes/competencies set in each program's CMO served as the basis for the crafting of the test. The researcher also considered the syllabus prepared by faculty member handling the subject. For stage 2, examination was made using a dichotomous type, specifically multiple-choice questions for parallel implementation. Test construction for stage 3 was guided by the table of specifications (TOS) prepared by the researcher which was checked by experts from other campuses of the university who are also handling the same subject. For the assessment and testing of the items, the researcher pilot-tested the instrument on 19 education students enrolled in Calculus III subjects who voluntarily allowed the researcher to obtain test results from their Calculus subject using purposive sampling similar to [12]. The researcher asked permission from the students to use their Midterm examination results as data input for the study. They were informed about the objectives and the assurance of confidentiality and anonymity. Likewise, no personal information was collected and used by the researcher. Then, the researcher used the item difficulty index, index of discrimination, distractor analysis, Kuder-Richardson 20, and Rasch model using the process of [13], [14], and [15]. After the validity, difficulty, and reliability checking, the researcher revised the items found not reliable, low-discriminating items from the results after stage 3. The obtained data were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) v29 and JAMOVI 2.3.28 software. Finally, the last stage is the administration of the examination to the intended students, which is beyond the scope of this paper. To perform the analysis and report accurately, test statistics were used to assess the performance of each test item using students' responses in the Calculus III test. Results are presented and reflected in the series of tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Item Difficulty Index

Item difficulty is the proportion of test takers who responded correctly to each item in the test [16]. The item difficulty index is interpreted from too difficult (0.30) to too easy (0.70) [17], [18], [19]. To declare that an item is at the average level of difficulty, the index should range from 30%-70%. Based on the results, the difficulty index shows that the test is relatively easy based on the frequency for each difficulty range category (70%-100%; f=34); (31%-69%; f=9); and (0%-30%; f=7).

The results of item analysis of the item difficulty index for Mathematics major students revealed that the examination is generally perceived as easy by the students. Despite this result, there are items that students found difficult, particularly in combining two concepts to answer a particular problem. For example, item number 13 is found difficult by the students. An analysis is presented below:

Item 13. Using L' Hopital rule, is the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \frac{5n+3}{2n-7}$ convergent or divergent?

- Convergent since the result after applying L' Hopital is greater than 0
- Divergent since the result after applying L' Hopital is greater than 0
- Convergent since the result after applying L' Hopital is lesser than 0
- Divergent since the result after applying L' Hopital is infinity.

This item tests the students' knowledge and understanding of two concepts in Calculus- the L'Hopital rule (used to find the derivative), and the basic theory of convergence. In this item, only 21% of students obtained the correct answer, reflecting their below-average competence in applying L'Hopital's rule in convergence tests.

Another significant finding is paying attention to small details. An example of this is item number 15, where there are only 26% of the students answered correctly. While the question only focused on finding an entry in the solution that makes it incorrect, the majority of the students answered the question incorrectly. This reveals that there are some small items that students overlooked, particularly in dealing with the solution. Though small in detail, small details in solving mathematical problems make a huge impact on the finality of the answer (e.g., misidentified sign [20]).

Item 15. What makes the solution incorrect about the $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{3^n}{n!}$ As a convergent series?

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Solution: } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{u_{n+1}}{u_n} &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{3^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} \cdot \frac{n!}{3^n} \right| \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{3^n(3)}{(n+1)(n)!} \cdot \frac{n!}{3^n} \right| \\ &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left| \frac{3}{n+1} \right| \\ &= \frac{3}{\infty} \\ &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

thus, convergence!

- n
- 3^n
- $n+1$
- The series diverges

Table 1. Item Distribution per Difficulty Index

Difficulty Range	Frequency	Percentage	Item Difficulty Index	Interpretation
70%-100% (Easy)	34	68.00%	75%	The test is relatively easy
30%-69% (Average)	9	18.00%		
0%-29% (Difficult)	7	14.00%		
Total	50	100.00%		

Item	Item Difficulty	Interpretation	Item	Item Difficulty	Interpretation
1	100.00%	Easy	26	68.00%	Average
2	95.00%	Easy	27	0.00%	Difficult
3	100.00%	Easy	28	95.00%	Easy
4	95.00%	Easy	29	89.00%	Easy
5	100.00%	Easy	30	89.00%	Easy
6	95.00%	Easy	31	95.00%	Easy
7	32.00%	Average	32	11.00%	Difficult
8	84.00%	Easy	33	95.00%	Easy
9	53.00%	Average	34	5.00%	Difficult
10	95.00%	Easy	35	95.00%	Easy
11	100.00%	Easy	36	95.00%	Easy
12	89.00%	Easy	37	84.00%	Easy
13	21.00%	Difficult	38	89.00%	Easy
14	53.00%	Average	39	100.00%	Easy
15	21.00%	Difficult	40	58.00%	Average
16	79.00%	Easy	41	58.00%	Average

17	79.00%	Easy	42	89.00%	Easy
18	26.00%	Difficult	43	89.00%	Easy
19	95.00%	Easy	44	100.00%	Easy
20	100.00%	Easy	45	95.00%	Easy
21	89.00%	Easy	46	42.00%	Average
22	63.00%	Average	47	89.00%	Easy
23	95.00%	Easy	48	21.00%	Difficult
24	95.00%	Easy	49	58.00%	Average
25	100.00%	Easy	50	89.00%	Easy

Item Discrimination Index

The discrimination index is the difference between the proportion of test takers in the upper 27% of the class who obtained the correct answer in each test item and the proportion of test takers in the lower 27% who answered correctly each test item. The discrimination index is an item's ability to discriminate between the upper and lower 27% of the test takers [4], [5], [21]. The value of the discrimination index ranges from -1.0 to +1.0. Negative discrimination index means that the item is poor and should be rejected or discarded. When the discrimination index is equal to zero, the item has no discriminating power, hence should also be removed from the test.

Results from Table 2 show that 22% of the items fall on 0.30 and above, while 40% of the items fall between 0.10 – 0.29. These items should be revised before inclusion to the examination. There are 15 items (30%) that show no discrimination, while 4 items showed a negative discrimination index (items 4,7,35,36).

These items classified as poor were answered correctly by the lower 27% of the students but incorrectly answered by students in the upper 27%. In this instance, the items are non-discriminatory and provide relatively little information about the competency, thus poorly discern the respondents' different trait levels [18].

Table 2. Item Distribution per Discrimination Index

Discrimination Index		Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage	Recommendation
0.30 and above		Good	11	22.00%	Include/retain
0.10 – 0.29		Fair	20	40.00%	Revise
Equal to 0		No Discrimination	15	30.00%	Discard/reject
Negative		Poor	4	8.00%	Discard/reject

Item No	Upper	Lower	Index of Discrimination	Interpretation	Item No	Upper	Lower	Index of Discrimination	Interpretation
1	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	26	80.00%	40.00%	0.40	Good
2	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair	27	0.00%	0.00%	0.00	No Discrimination
3	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	28	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
4	80.00%	100.00%	-0.20	Poor	29	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
5	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	30	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good
6	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	31	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
7	20.00%	40.00%	-0.20	Poor	32	20.00%	0.00%	0.20	Fair
8	80.00%	80.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	33	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination
9	80.00%	40.00%	0.40	Good	34	0.00%	0.00%	0.00	No Discrimination
10	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair	35	80.00%	100.00%	-0.20	Poor
11	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No Discrimination	36	80.00%	100.00%	-0.20	Poor
12	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair	37	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good
13	40.00%	20.00%	0.20	Fair	38	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
14	60.00%	40.00%	0.20	Fair	39	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	No

						%	%		
15	40.00%	20.00%	0.20	Fair No	40	80.00%	60.00%	0.20	Discrimination Fair
16	80.00%	80.00%	0.00	Discrimination	41	80.00%	20.00%	0.60	Good
17	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good	42	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
18	40.00%	20.00%	0.20	Fair No	43	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good No
19	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	Discrimination No	44	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	Discrimination
20	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	Discrimination	45	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair
21	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good	46	60.00%	0.00%	0.60	Good
22	80.00%	60.00%	0.20	Fair	47	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good
23	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair	48	40.00%	20.00%	0.20	Fair
24	100.00%	80.00%	0.20	Fair No	49	60.00%	40.00%	0.20	Fair
25	100.00%	100.00%	0.00	Discrimination	50	100.00%	60.00%	0.40	Good

Distracter Analysis

Table 3 shows the distribution of items per non-functional distractor (NFD). A total of 150 distractors were analyzed, where 70 (46.67%) were chosen by more than 5% of the test takers, while 80 (53.33%) were classified as non-functional distractors. Non-functional distractors (NFD) are those distractors chosen by less than 5% of examinees that need to be re-evaluated [22]. Based on the results, there are 6 (12%) items with no NFDs. Test items with 1-NFD comprised 32.00% of the total number of items. Items with 2-NFDs comprised 40% while 3-NFDs consisted of 16% of the total items.

Distracter analysis opens opportunity to teachers and test developers to understand why students obtained incorrect responses about each test item, and further determine areas requiring improvement or other appropriate actions [23]. In the result of the present study, while students found the test, relatively easy, there are distracters that possess characteristics to distinguish those who know and do not know the underlying concepts or those who are certain versus those who made a random guessing. Random guessing is influenced by the complexity of item contents [24].

Table 3. Distribution of Items per Non-Functional Distracter

Number of Non-Functional Distracters					Frequency				Percentage	
Three					8				16.00%	
Two					20				40.00%	
One					16				32.00%	
Zero					6				12.00%	
Values					Interpretation/Recommendation				Frequency of Non- Functional Distracters	Average % of Non- Functional Distracters for
Test	A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D		
1	0.00%	CA	0.00%	0.00%	Revise	CA	Revise	Revise	3	100.00
2	0.00%	5.26%	CA	0.00%	Revise	Retain	CA	Revise	2	66.67
3	0.00%	CA	0.00%	0.00%	Revise	CA	Revise	Revise	3	100.00
4	0.00%	0.00%	CA	5.26%	Revise	Revise	CA	Retain	2	66.67
5	CA	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Revise	Revise	3	100.00
6	0.00%	CA	5.26%	0.00%	Revise	CA	Retain	Revise	2	66.67
7	0.00%	0.00%	31.58%	CA	Retain	Retain	CA	CA	1	33.33

					Revise						
8	0.00%	5.26%	10.53%	CA	Revise	Retain	Retain	CA	1	33.33	
9	0.00%	5.26%	CA	42.11%	Revise	Retain	CA	Retain	1	33.33	
10	5.26%	CA	0.00%	0.00%	Retain	CA	Revise	Revise	2	66.67	
11	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Revise	Revise	CA	3	100.00	
12	0.00%	0.00%	10.53%	CA	Revise	Revise	Retain	CA	2	66.67	
13	10.53%	CA	5.26%	63.16%	Retain	CA	Retain	Retain	0	0.00	
14	CA	0.00%	47.37%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Retain	Revise	2	66.67	
15	CA	26.32%	10.53%	42.11%	CA	Retain	Retain	Retain	0	0.00	
16	5.26%	10.53%	CA	5.26%	Retain	Retain	CA	Retain	0	0.00	
17	15.79%	5.26%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
18	10.53%	21.05%	CA	42.11%	Retain	Retain	CA	Retain	0	0.00	
19	0.00%	0.00%	5.26%	CA	Revise	Revise	Retain	CA	2	66.67	
20	CA	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Revise	Revise	3	100.00	
21	5.26%	5.26%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
22	CA	36.84%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Retain	Revise	Revise	2	66.67	
23	0.00%	CA	0.00%	5.26%	Revise	CA	Revise	Retain	2	66.67	
24	0.00%	5.26%	CA	0.00%	Revise	Retain	CA	Revise	2	66.67	
25	CA	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Revise	Revise	3	100.00	
26	26.32%	5.26%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
27	68.42%	CA	10.53%	21.05%	Retain	CA	Retain	Retain	0	0.00	
28	CA	0.00%	5.26%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Retain	Revise	2	66.67	
29	5.26%	CA	5.26%	0.00%	Retain	CA	Retain	Revise	1	33.33	
30	0.00%	0.00%	CA	10.53%	Revise	Revise	CA	Retain	2	66.67	
31	0.00%	CA	0.00%	5.26%	Revise	CA	Revise	Retain	2	66.67	
32	84.21%	0.00%	5.26%	CA	Retain	Revise	Retain	CA	1	33.33	
33	0.00%	0.00%	CA	5.26%	Revise	Revise	CA	Retain	2	66.67	
34	21.05%	73.68%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
35	CA	0.00%	5.26%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Retain	Revise	2	66.67	
36	0.00%	0.00%	CA	5.26%	Revise	Revise	CA	Retain	2	66.67	
37	0.00%	CA	5.26%	10.53%	Revise	CA	Retain	Retain	1	33.33	
38	0.00%	CA	5.26%	5.26%	Revise	CA	Retain	Retain	1	33.33	
39	CA	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	CA	Revise	Revise	Revise	3	100.00	
40	31.58%	10.53%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA		1	33.33	

								Revise			
41	5.26%	36.84%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
42	10.53%	CA	0.00%	0.00%	Retain	CA	Revise	Revise	2	66.67	
43	0.00%	CA	0.00%	10.53%	Revise	CA	Revise	Retain	2	66.67	
44	0.00%	0.00%	CA	0.00%	Revise	Revise	CA	Revise	3	100.00	
45	0.00%	CA	0.00%	5.26%	Revise	CA	Revise	Retain	2	66.67	
46	26.32%	31.58%	CA	0.00%	Retain	Retain	CA	Revise	1	33.33	
47	CA	0.00%	0.00%	10.53%	CA	Revise	Revise	Retain	2	66.67	
48	63.16%	0.00%	CA	15.79%	Retain	Revise	CA	Retain	1	33.33	
49	10.53%	CA	21.05%	10.53%	Retain	CA	Retain	Retain	0	0.00	
50	CA	5.26%	5.26%	0.00%	CA	Retain	Retain	Revise	1	33.33	

CA-Correct Answer

Reliability Analysis

Reliability shows to what extent scores yielded by an instrument are distributed to a certain population, given a particular time, and conditions are consistent and reproducible [25]. There is a moderate reliability of the test (KR=0.55) based on the reliability categorization presented in the study of [26], [27]. In estimating the reliability coefficient, KR-20 was used as it is more appropriate to use when items are dichotomously scored (*right, wrong; correct, incorrect*) [28]. Another consideration of the use of KR-20 is the level of difficulty of each item based on the table of specifications (TOS) that is also aligned with the competencies set by the curriculum.

The value of the test given to the students showed moderate reliability, which implies convergence of the items in measuring the competency in the Calculus subject. This result denotes that items, in general, are acceptable to be given to students and are appropriate in measuring students' competency.

Table 4. Estimation of Reliability Coefficient through Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20)

Test		Sum of pq	Variance of Scores	No. of Items	KR-20	Verbal Interpretation	
Calculus III		5.07	11.04	50	0.55	Moderate Reliability	
Item	p	q	Pq	Item	p	q	pq
1	1.000	0.000	0.000	26	0.684	0.316	0.216
2	0.947	0.053	0.050	27	0.000	1.000	0.000
3	1.000	0.000	0.000	28	0.947	0.053	0.050
4	0.947	0.053	0.050	29	0.895	0.105	0.094
5	1.000	0.000	0.000	30	0.895	0.105	0.094
6	0.947	0.053	0.050	31	0.947	0.053	0.050
7	0.316	0.684	0.216	32	0.105	0.895	0.094
8	0.842	0.158	0.133	33	0.947	0.053	0.050
9	0.526	0.474	0.249	34	0.053	0.947	0.050
10	0.947	0.053	0.050	35	0.947	0.053	0.050
11	1.000	0.000	0.000	36	0.947	0.053	0.050
12	0.895	0.105	0.094	37	0.842	0.158	0.133
13	0.211	0.789	0.166	38	0.895	0.105	0.094
14	0.526	0.474	0.249	39	1.000	0.000	0.000
15	0.211	0.789	0.166	40	0.579	0.421	0.244
16	0.789	0.211	0.166	41	0.579	0.421	0.244
17	0.789	0.211	0.166	42	0.895	0.105	0.094
18	0.263	0.737	0.194	43	0.895	0.105	0.094
19	0.947	0.053	0.050	44	1.000	0.000	0.000
20	1.000	0.000	0.000	45	0.947	0.053	0.050
21	0.895	0.105	0.094	46	0.421	0.579	0.244
22	0.632	0.368	0.233	47	0.895	0.105	0.094

23	0.947	0.053	0.050	48	0.211	0.789	0.166
24	0.947	0.053	0.050	49	0.579	0.421	0.244
25	1.000	0.000	0.000	50	0.895	0.105	0.094

Rasch Analysis

In addition to helping create a curriculum that is more responsive and flexible, the Rasch Model promotes the development of more targeted and efficient teaching methods that are tailored to the needs of each student [29]. Rasch modeling is found developed a valid and reliable mathematics measurement instrument [30].

Initially, there are 50 items in the test. In consideration of the assumption of data fitness, items where all students answered correctly were removed from the number of items run in the JAMOVI software for Rasch Analysis. The total number of items run in the JAMOVI software from 50 was reduced to 36. For the purpose of mapping convenience, the item number did not change. One of the important considerations in using the Rasch model is the 'fit' or how the data fit the Rasch Model.

Based on the presented data in the table 5, the p-value of 0.054 (Person = 0.632) denotes no deviation of the data from the Rasch Model. In analyzing specific item fit using the outlier-sensitive fit (outfit), there are four outfit values greater than 1.30 [15] that do not fit the model. These items include items 6, 19, 35, and 36. Figures 1 & 2 show that for the item measures, results revealed that item number 32 is the most difficult to endorse, based on a value of 2.296, while items 2, 10, 31, 24, 28, 23, and 45 are the easiest items to endorse, with values equivalent to -3.075.

Table 5. Analysis of Data Using the Rasch Model

Model Fit		Person Reliability		p-value	Interpretation
Scale		0.632		0.054	Data fit the Rasch Model
Item Number	Proportion	Measure	S.E. Measure	Infit	Outfit
36	0.947	-3.075	1.040	1.118	3.373
35	0.947	-3.075	1.040	1.074	1.508
6	0.947	-3.075	1.040	1.064	1.392
19	0.947	-3.075	1.040	1.066	1.356
2	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.957	0.610
10	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.957	0.610
31	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.957	0.610
24	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.951	0.605
28	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.951	0.605
23	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.902	0.480
45	0.947	-3.075	1.040	0.902	0.480
12	0.895	-2.300	0.764	1.091	1.185
38	0.895	-2.300	0.764	1.018	1.036
42	0.895	-2.300	0.764	1.006	0.934
21	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.979	0.817
29	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.930	0.763
50	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.911	0.630
47	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.905	0.627
43	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.855	0.552
30	0.895	-2.300	0.764	0.849	0.549
37	0.842	-1.811	0.647	0.899	0.784
17	0.789	-1.436	0.582	0.914	0.839
26	0.684	-0.843	0.515	0.997	1.042
27	0.684	-0.843	0.515	0.989	0.963
22	0.632	-0.588	0.497	0.982	0.951
49	0.579	-0.346	0.486	1.117	1.181
40	0.579	-0.346	0.486	1.099	1.101
41	0.579	-0.346	0.486	0.923	0.933
14	0.526	-0.113	0.481	1.123	1.142
9	0.526	-0.113	0.481	1.025	1.029
46	0.421	0.351	0.486	1.034	1.010
18	0.263	1.123	0.540	1.064	1.150
48	0.211	1.436	0.581	1.085	1.244
13	0.211	1.436	0.581	1.042	1.199
15	0.211	1.436	0.581	1.037	1.148
32	0.105	2.296	0.762	1.085	1.119

Figure 1. Wright Map for the 36-item examination for the Calculus subject
 Source: JAMOVI Software

Figure 2. Expected Scores Curve for items 2 (Easiest to Endorse) and 32 (Most Difficult to Endorse)
 Source: JAMOVI Software

Table 6 shows the considerations for the non-inclusion of items from the test draft. Giving consideration to item difficulty, when the item difficulty index is easy or difficult, the item can be considered for non-inclusion. In terms of item discrimination, when an item shows no discrimination, it can be considered for non-inclusion. However, when an item has poor item discrimination, it is automatically not included due to the issue of negative discrimination value. As to functional distracters, when an item has no functional distracter, it is excluded from the test draft. The Kuder-Richardson 20 value is not actually included as a criterion for specific item but should show acceptable value for reliability for the test to be declared as reliable. Finally, when an item shows ‘no fit’ after subjecting Rasch Analysis specifically using Outlier-Sensitive Fit (Outfit) measures, it is excluded from the test draft. Hence, regardless whether the item passed item difficulty, discrimination, has functional distracters, if it does not fit in the Rasch model, then it is removed from the test draft.

Out of 50 items in the test draft, there are 19 items that are recommended for removal. These 19 items did not pass the 3D-KRM analysis. Therefore, the final test includes 31 distinct items that can be distributed to Mathematics majors in the succeeding academic year.

Table 6. Consideration for Non-Inclusion of Item from the Test Draft

Item	Item Difficulty	Item Discrimination	Functional Distractors	KR-20 Value	Rasch Model	Action
1	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
3	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
4	Easy	Poor	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
5	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
6	Easy	No Discrimination	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
7	Average	Poor	2	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
8	Easy	No Discrimination	2	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
11	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
16	Easy	No Discrimination	3	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
19	Easy	No Discrimination	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
20	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
25	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
27	Difficult	No Discrimination	3	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
33	Easy	No Discrimination	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
34	Difficult	No Discrimination	2	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
35	Easy	Poor	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
36	Easy	Poor	1	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
39	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft
44	Easy	No Discrimination	0	0.55	Not Fit	Remove from the Test Draft

CONCLUSION

Analysis using item difficulty index, discrimination, distractors' efficiency, Kuder-Richardson 20, and Rasch model (3D-KRM) provides converging results about the psychometric properties of term examination in Calculus subject for Mathematics major students. In order to increase the objectivity of the assessment tool given to students, the instrument should pass each series of steps in the test construction method. Out of 50 items, 31 items were considered in the final draft of the test. This test will be administered to the mathematics majors in the next academic year.

Despite the limitation specifically in the number of respondents, this study showed how the item difficulty index, index of discrimination, distractor's efficiency measure, Kuder-Richardson 20, and Rasch model (3D-KRM) results converge to estimate psychometric properties of the test. For this reason, educators may utilize the processes and results presented and discussed in this attempt for further test enhancement. A policy for the education department and other departments may also be proposed to strengthen test construction procedures for term examinations to increase the objectivity and reliability of tests given to tertiary students.

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